

IBPG - Darwin

The Institute of Biopaleogeography
named under Charles R. Darwin

IBPG 16 (2022) 1-68

E-ISSN 2956-4573

The unsurpassable natural beauty of the Plitviče Lakes National Park, in Croatia

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Publisher's Address:

Scientific Publishing House DARWIN at The Institute,
22, Adama Mickiewicza Street, 78-520 Złocieniec,
District Drawski, West Pomerania, Poland

Cite of this article:

Fabio Rossano Dario, Maria Cristina Veiga De Vincenzo. The unsurpassable natural beauty of the Plitviče Lakes National Park, in Croatia. *The Institute of Biopaleogeography named under Charles R. Darwin 16 (2022) 1-68*

ABSTRACT

This paper is both, a photographic summary of a scientific and a touristic expedition carried out in October 2019 in Plitviče Lakes National Park, the oldest and the largest national park in the Republic of Croatia, to know the natural beauties and structure of this UNESCO World Heritage. Plitviče Lakes National Park consists of 16 crystalline lakes, emerald-blue colored and connected by a series of more than 90 cascades and waterfalls. The photos show some of the park structures and the wilderness areas, with spacious forest complexes, among which lakes, small streams, and waterfalls extend, besides geological formations and hydrogeological karst phenomenon, species of plants, and birds.

Keywords: Plitviče Lakes, National Park, Croatia, protected area

INTRODUCTION

Plitviče Lakes National Park is known for its natural beauty. Situated at the Bosnia Herzegovina border, about halfway between Zadar and Zagreb (Figure 1), it is the jewel of the mountainous central Croatia, and it is easy to see why it was registered in 1979 as a UNESCO World Heritage. It is the oldest nature park in Southeast Europe, founded in 1949 when there was still Yugoslavia. The protected area extends over 296.85 square kilometers (73,350 acres) [1].

The main objective of this scientific and touristic expedition, realized in October 2019 was to know the natural beauties of the different ecosystems and the structure existing in this Park, identifying and photographing the beauties of nature accessible to our lens and the main plant and animal species that we were lucky to see.

Highlights within the park include Veliki Slap, also known as the Great Waterfall (Photo 87). From certain viewpoints, the Sastavci waterfalls appear to be an extension of this, creating a dramatic scene from which the Korana River springs up and flows north. Numerous viewpoints throughout the park provide stunning views. The eastern ridge of the canyon which overlooks the Lower Lakes provides particularly beautiful views which will surely be familiar to those who have seen images of the park in magazines, sites or on postcards.

Plitviče Lakes are located in the forested mountainous region of Croatia. The lakes flow from different rivers and streams and they are joined together by cascades and waterfalls, the lower cluster formed by runoff from the mountains, descending from an altitude of 636 to 503 m (2,087 to 1,650 ft) over a distance of some 8 kilometers (5.0 mi). The lakes of Plitviče cover an area of about 200 ha (0.77 square miles), and the water exiting from the lowest lake forms the Korana River. The lakes are renowned for their distinctive colors, ranging from azure to green, grey, or blue. The colors change constantly depending on the number of minerals or organisms in the water and the angle of sunlight.

According to Köppen's classification, the climate type prevailing in the Plitviče Lakes National Park is Cfb (moderately warm and humid, with hot summers). The average annual rainfall is 1,550 mm. Apart from being defined by latitude, height above sea level, ground inclination, and sun exposure, the prevailing vegetation is also defined by geologic bedrocks, soil, and the farming methods used. Limestone and dolomitic rocks of various ages (Triassic,

Jurassic, Cretaceous) make up the geological bedrock. Considering the relief, climate, and land farming in the recent past, vast forest surfaces in their various stages: from thicket to virgin forest (Čorkova uvala virgin forest) have remained very well preserved (3/4 of the Park's surface area).

Figure 1. Localization of the Plitviče Lakes National Park, Republic of Croatia.
<http://maps.yandex.com>

The Plitviče Lakes National Park includes large forest complexes between which stretch lakes and waterfalls, along which there are many forest paths and wooden bridges, lakes and small streams. Lots of wooden footbridges and pathways meander over the lakes and around their shores creating gentle trails for visitors to wander, explore, and take in the views. Portions of the park are also connected by boats (Photos 4-6). The walking trails in the park are well maintained and safe. The vast majority of the paths are flat, though in some areas you may find stairs or an incline. In general, however, the trails are not challenging and appropriate for a variety of ages and fitness levels. Wooden trails meander over the lakes while dirt paths or stone walkways connect other areas (Photos 31-41, 66, 69-73, 76-100).

More than 1,400 plant taxa (species and subspecies) have been recorded for the Plitviče Lakes National Park, which amounts to 30% of the entire Croatian flora. This can be explained by its specific geographic location (approx. 55 km air distance from the sea in the inland of Croatia's longest and highest mountain, Velebit, on the slopes of Mala Kapela and Lička

Plješevica, at an altitude of 369 to 1,279 m above sea level), as well as by geomorphological, climatological and ecological factors. This is an area of alpine topography that exerts a considerable impact on climatic phenomena and consequently, on the vegetation of the area. Species of various distributions and flora elements can be found within the small Park area: Mediterranean, Mediterranean-Atlantic, Illyrian, Balkanic, Carpathian, Eurasian, Circulatory, and Boreal. The Park's flora is also characterized by the diversity of orchids (more than 60 taxa).

The beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) is the predominant tree species in the Plitviče Lakes National Park. It is a large tree, normally grows to 25-35 m (82-115 ft) tall and up to 1.5 m (4.9 ft) trunk diameter, but in rare instances, it may of reaching heights of up to 50 m (160 ft) tall and 3 m (9.8 ft) trunk diameter. The leaves of beech are often not abscised (dropped) in the autumn and instead remain on the tree until the spring [8]. Because beech trees live for so long, they provide gnarled and knotted habitats for some deadwood specialists, such as hole-nesting birds and wood-boring insects. The bark is often home to a variety of fungi, mosses, and lichens [9-11].

Looking at the Park's forest zones, we come across the beech zone (predominant) and the European silver fir zone, which both represent a permanent vegetation form or climate-zonal vegetation (Photo 36). The European silver fir (*Abies alba*) is a large evergreen coniferous tree growing to 40–50 m (130-160 ft) (exceptionally 60 m (200 ft)) tall and with a trunk diameter up to 1.5 m (4 ft 11 in). It occurs at altitudes of 300-1,700 m (980-5,580 ft) (over 500 m (1,600 ft)), on mountains with rainfall over 1,000 millimetres (39 in) per year [12, 13].

As a long-lived tree, the fir is considered a significant ecological and functional species, which stabilizes soils and retains water. The fir is also considered a fundamental species for maintaining high biodiversity in forest ecosystems because of its shade tolerance, ability to survive long periods in the understory and to respond when light conditions become more favorable, plasticity to environmental conditions, and ability to coexist with many tree species [14]. Both fir and beech, as the main coexisting species in montane, mixed-species forests, are shade tolerant and could thrive under conditions of deep shade for longer periods [15, 16].

Within these beech and European silver fir forests, a range of non-zonal flora is developed concerning relief, geological background, soil depth, soil moisture, e.g., willow (*Salix alba*), European alder (*Alnus glutinosa*), hop-hornbeam (*Ostrya carpinifolia*), and spruce forests (*Picea excelsa*). Hop hornbeam is a small to medium-sized deciduous tree Betulaceae family, native to southern Europe, the Balkans, Western Asia, and the Caucasus region. It often grows in rocky, shallow, and poor limestone soils and usually on sunny hillsides facing south or as a dominating species in the understorey of sub-Mediterranean forests [17].

The forests of the Plitviče Lakes National Park apart from representing habitats for such an abundance of forest flora are also home to various wildlife species. Being very well preserved, and nearly pristine, these ecosystems are crucial in nature and wildlife diversity preservation. The Park has a relatively low number of plant endemic species (approx. 1.7%), but this number should not be neglected as a lot of very interesting species are present: the Dalmatian Scilla *Chouardia litardierei*, the lacy hellebore *Helleborus multifidus*, the Croatian carnation *Dianthus croaticus* [18], the fumewort *Corydalis solida*, among others.

The Park is the only site of the globally critically endangered Siberian leopard plant *Ligularia sibirica*. It is a perennial herbaceous plant, native to fens and damp grassy meadows in Siberia, Central, and Eastern Europe. Once fairly common, it has disappeared from many places in Europe, owing to drainage of wetlands and competition from other plants invading its natural habitats [19].

Plitviče Lakes National Park as a part of the ecological network Natura 2000 is significant for three target species along with the Siberian leopard plant: the creeping marshwort *Apium repens*, the Dalmatian Scilla *Chouardia litardierei*, and the lady's-slipper orchid *Cypripedium calceolus*. In Croatia and beyond, the densest known populations of the lady's-slipper orchid *Cypripedium calceolus*, one of the most endangered and most beautiful European orchids [20, 21], are found in the forest habitats of the Park.

Bog habitats and their vegetation in Croatia, as well as in the Park, are relicts of the glacial period. Croatia is the southern limit of the distribution of this habitat type, characteristic of Central and Northern Europe (Photo 72). They are present in small areas and are highly dependent on microclimate conditions. Highly specialized and very rare plant species, nowadays endangered, depend on this type of habitat: peat moss (*Sphagnum* sp), the common sundew *Drosera rotundifolia*, the common butterwort *Pinguicula vulgaris*, the lesser bladderwort *Utricularia minor*, and many other species [22]. They are at risk of extinction due to specific conditions. They can only be preserved by applying active protective measures (maintaining a favorable water regime and removing part of the vegetation). In addition to species from the plant and animal world, the Park is also abundant in fungi species. Fungi are a large and very significant group of organisms (Photo 55).

The fauna, which represents the wildlife of the Plitviče Lakes, is extremely rich and diverse due to the conservation and sustainability of the habitat. There are many species of insects, like 321 species of butterflies, with the emphasis being given to the butterflies *Phengaris alcon alcon*, *Phengaris arioni*, and *Phengaris alcon rebeli*. One of the most sensitive and endangered species is *Phengaris alcon alcon*, which is on the Convention list for the protection of Europe's wild fauna and natural habitats. Some other interesting insects are the Trichoptera which contains one specific endemic species, and the Carabidae (an important family of beetles) which are excellent indicators of habitat quality [23].

Invertebrates living in Plitviče Lakes are mostly inhabitants of the aquatic parts of the park and two groups of these species are strictly protected and endangered. These species are the broad-fingered crayfish *Astacus astacus*, the most common species of crayfish in Europe, a traditional food source, and the stone crayfish *Austropotamobius torrentium*. Like other true crayfish, the broad-fingered crayfish are restricted to fresh water, living only in unpolluted streams, rivers, and lakes [24]. The stone crayfish is also a European species of freshwater crayfish from the family Astacidae. It is mostly found in tributaries of the Danube, having originated in the northern part of the Balkan Peninsula [25].

There are only a few fish species living in Plitviče Lake's water. It is still an unexplained issue as to whether they have been living in this space since ancient times. The first research on the ichthyofauna of the Plitviče Lakes was conducted in the thirties and fifties [26-28]. The most common fish species in Plitviče Lakes are the chub (*Squalius cephalus*) (Photo 62), Neretva roach (*Rutilus pigus*), and Marsilijev pijor (*Phoxinus phoxinus*), crvenperka (*Scardinius erythrophthalmus*), and the trout. Not all lakes of Plitviče are suitable for trouts to feed and breed. The most suitable lake is Prošćansko Jezero (jezero means lake in the Croatian language), which is rich with plankton crabs, which trouts eat [29, 30].

The Plitviče Lakes and their tributaries have all the main characteristics of typical trout mountain water. Brown trout (*Salmo trutta*) is one of the Aboriginal inhabitants of these lakes, and it comes in two forms: *Salmo trutta fario* and *Salmo trutta lacustris*. Local people can recognize which trout is from which lake and which from tributaries, based on color composition and body shape [31, 32].

Intending to enrich the lakes, species of fish were introduced into the water of Plitviče, like Jezerska Zlatoovcica, more known as Arctic charr (*Salvelinus alpinus*), a fish of prey from North America, as well as Californian trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) which have been raised in the Park for years, and nowadays is naturally increasing in number [33, 34]. A carp species have been recently noticed in the lake, such as those already mentioned *Squalius cephalus* and *Scardinius erythrophthalmus*. These species are, by the way, characteristic of low-land watercourses, so their presence is a consequence of both climatic changes and man's influence on these areas [35]. Fishing is prohibited in the Park, trying that this area keeps the characteristics of untouched nature.

In the Plitviče Lakes National Park there are 14 amphibians, of which are six listed in the Convention on the Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats. Fire salamander (*Salamandra salamandra*) is the most frequent species of salamanders that can be seen in springtime on walkways and roads. It is black with showy yellow stripes to varying degrees. This conspicuous coloration acts to deter predators by honest signaling its toxicity, and this salamander can have a very long lifespan, more than 50 years [36].

Other interesting amphibian species in Plitviče Lakes are *Salamandra atra* (alpine salamander), *Triturus carnifex* (crested newt) [37], and *Pelophylax kurtmuelleri* (Balkan lake frog) [38]. The alpine salamander is a shiny black salamander found in the Dinaric Alps at the eastern end of its range, at altitudes above 700 m (2,300 ft) [39]. The Balkan Lake frog occurs from sea level up to about 1000 m (3,280 ft), but larger populations are not found higher than 600 m (1,968 ft) [40]. The newts more frequent are the mountain newt (*Triturus alpestris*), and the ordinary newt (*Triturus vulgaris*), just as the most frequent frogs are the European common frog (*Rana temporaris*) and the agile frog (*Rana dalmatina*) [41-45]. The biggest frog in this area is the European toad (*Bufo bufo*), which is easy to find in the forests and in damp park sections where it hides during the day, in small rodent holes [46-48].

Reptiles are represented in a small number of species in the Plitviče Lakes National Park. Long winters and thick snow cover are decreasing the number of this group of vertebrates. There are also a total of 14 reptile species, of which are 9 on the Convention on the Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats, while 10 have the status of a severely endangered species. Some of the interesting species of lizards are *Zootoca vivipara* (common lizard) and *Iberolacerta horvathi* (Horvath's rock lizard). *Zootoca vivipara* is the only reptile that lives on the top of the mountains and far, in the north of Europe [49], but it can be seen in the Park.

The Horvath's rock lizard is a lizard native to northwestern Croatia, Slovenia, and the adjoining parts of northeastern Italy and southern Austria. It is a rock specialist and is very agile, even leaping into the air to catch prey [50]. There are also two poisonous snakes recorded in the Plitviče Lakes National Park, namely the *Vipera ammodytes* (horned viper), whose main distribution area is on the Balkan Peninsula [51], and the *Vipera berus* (common viper) [52].

The *Vipera ammodytes* are quite frequent species and can be seen particularly in spring, in places exposed to the sun. It is the most venomous and most dangerous snake in Europe [53, 54]. In the lake, beside reeds and thick water vegetation, some of the turtles (*Emys orbicularis*) [55-57] could be found as well. Besides almost all the Park waters, a common one is the snake species "ribarica" (*Natrix tessellata*) [58] which is exclusively fed by fish catching them by diving in or from the shore. It often provokes people's fear, due to external similarities with a poisonous snake (*Vipera berus*).

The ornithofauna of the Plitviče Lakes is rich and diverse, comprising 168 bird species. Due to the preservation and the size of the forest habitats (around 76% of the surface), there is

great diversity and abundance of species related to forest habitats. The species include twelve species of raptors, eight species of owls, and nine species of woodpeckers. Some of the most interesting species are *Buteo buteo* (common buzzard), *Strix uralensis* (Ural owl), *Strix aluco* (brown owl), *Glaucidium passerinum* (Eurasian pygmy owl), *Asio otus* (long-eared owl), *Aegolius funereus* (boreal owl), *Erithacus rubecula* (robin) (Photo 63), *Cinclus cinclus* (white-throated dipper), *Poecile palustris* (marsh titmouse), *Poecile montanus* (mountain titmouse), *Motacilla cinerea* (mountain wagtail).

The *Buteo buteo* is a medium-to-large bird of prey that has a large range. The species lives in most of Europe, and generally inhabits the interface of woodlands and open grounds; most typically the species lives on forest edges [59]. The density of the common buzzard populations (5.4 pairs per 10 km²) in beech-fir forests in the northwestern area of the Plitviče Lakes National Park is the greatest recorded density of this species in Croatia and among the greatest ones in Europe. The *Glaucidium passerinum* is known as the smallest European owl, and it is found in the boreal forests of Northern and Central Europe to Siberia [60].

The list of endangered birds in the national park includes nesting birds, the most endangered of which is the *Pernis apivorus* (European honey buzzard). As particularly important and rare, should mention the woodpeckers *Dendrocopos leucotos* (white-backed woodpecker), and *Dryocopus martius* (black woodpecker), who live in mature and well-preserved forests [61, 62].

In the Park space, we can also find the treecreepers *Certhia familiaris* (kratkokljuni puzavac) and *Certhia brachydactyla* (dugokljuni puzavac).

In the silence of the Park, one can often hear a wood grouse (*Tetrao urogallus*) [63, 64]. This bird is mostly staying in hidden spots. In the past times, wood grouse used to live in almost all European forests, while today it is confined to certain well-preserved areas. It is a member of the grouse family and the largest of all extant grouse species. Mammalian predators known to take wood grouse include Eurasian lynx (*Lynx lynx*) [65-67] and gray wolf (*Canis lupus*) [68-72]. Meanwhile, European pine martens (*Martes martes*) [73, 74], beech martens (*Martes foina*) [75], brown bears (*Ursus arctos*) [76-82], wild boars (*Sus scrofa*) [83-87], and red foxes (*Vulpes vulpes*) [88-90] take mostly eggs and chicks but can attack adults too.

Several scientific papers have revealed the significant effect of large carnivores' on the dynamics and balance of ecosystems. Their importance has been proved in the maintenance of biodiversity, limiting the spread of infectious diseases and alien species [91], but also in securing the physical and chemical states of soil, water, and air [92]. Top predators, like Eurasian lynx, gray wolf, and brown bear have played and still have an important evolutionary role in the development and maintaining viable populations of their prey species. In European Union, lynx, wolf, and brown bear are protected by the Habitat Directive with the application of both habitat and individual protection.

The combination of intensive persecution, habitat loss, and prey deficiency led to the extinction of Eurasian lynx (*Lynx lynx*) in the Dinaric Mountains at the beginning of the 20th century [93]. In 1973, the population was reestablished by reintroducing animals from the Slovakian Carpathian Mountains into Slovenia, from where the animals spread into Croatia and Bosnia and Herzegovina [94]. Since the end of the 20th century the introduced population has been decreasing. Most deaths were human-related (92.7%).

The shooting was the most dominant cause of death (73.7%) [95, 96]. In the majority of Europe lynx mostly feeds on small and medium-sized ungulates, which make up 52-92% of lynx prey [97-99]. Regional variation in the proportion of ungulates in the lynx diet depends on

the availability of alternative prey, mainly hares [100]. Home-range sizes, movements, and daily activity of wolves (*Canis lupus*) were studied in Dalmatia, Croatia. The total home ranges of two packs were mean of 150.5 km². Core areas were 26.2 km² and 3.3 km². Differences in core area sizes were influenced by human activity-hunting and sheep grazing. Home range, seasonal variations in home-range size, habitat use, and activity of wolves in Dalmatia were oriented to avoid possible anthropic problems and also to benefit from human-related food sources [101].

Wolf is a generalist predator with a broad specter of prey items, and it takes opportunistically the most available food in a given place and time. The Wolf diet can contain both large prey animals like moose, deer, or wild boar as well as small rodents, invertebrates, carrion, and vegetal food [102]. In Europe wild ungulates (reindeer, moose, and various deer species) are the main prey item while beavers, hares, fox, raccoon dogs, domestic animals, and livestock have secondary importance. Red deer is the preferred species of prey compared to the roe deer. Moose or wild boar prevails only in regions without deer or where deer population densities are low [103]. Red deer have been the main and preferred prey item in the Polish Carpathian region [104], roe deer in Central and Western Poland [105], moose in the Finnish taiga [106], and wild boar in Byelorussia [107].

In most of Europe, true wilderness areas do not exist, and brown bears generally have to cope with human disturbance and infrastructure. The few studies in Europe that have investigated brown bear activity have demonstrated a predominantly nocturnal and 'shy' behavior in bears. There is still quite a debate on whether the shy, nocturnal bears of Europe are the result of centuries of persecution by men or whether hunting and the high disturbance potential in the multi-use landscapes are the driving force [108].

Regardless of its inclusion in the order Carnivora brown bear is a typical omnivore in terms of food preference, set of teeth, and digestive duct. Although the majority of bear food is vegetal, bears are not able to decompose cellulose while they can acquire plant sugars and the majority of vegetal proteins. The annual diet cycle has three main phases: a poor period in spring after hibernation, a normal foraging period in summer, and an active foraging period in autumn when winter reserves are collected. Plants are predominating in spring and summer while in late summer and autumn food of higher energy content, e.g berries, fruits, and grain is consumed. Meat, in form of kill and carrion, is easily digestible and high-energy food and is thus an important addition to the main diet in spring and autumn. Bears are not very effective predators compared to e.g., wolves and lynx. Most of the animal food consists of invertebrates, especially ants. At the same time, moose can locally form a substantial proportion of the bear diet in Sweden [109-114].

An interesting fact is that the black stork (*Ciconia nigra*) builds its nest in quiet forestry areas of the Park, but as a rule, it is done in lowland forests. These species have found the necessary living space in the Plitviče Lakes Park. Grasslands (meadows and pastures) make up 23% of the Park's area. They are important for three species of birds: the Montagu's harrier (*Circus pygargus*), the short-eared owl (*Asio flammeus*), and the corn crane (*Crex crex*). The Montagu's harrier has a particularly graceful flight, with powerful and elegant wingbeats [115]. Grassland areas are also extremely important to other birds, such as raptors and mammals, like foxes (*Vulpes vulpes*), roe deer (*Capreolus capreolus*), and bears (*Ursus arctos*), as well as insects (bees, butterflies, etc.), for finding food.

Flocks of wild ducks (*Anas platyrhynchos*) are frequent (Photo 61). Occasionally, duck "glavata" (*Aythya ferina*) lands there, as well as some lonely common heron (*Ardea cinerea*),

black-throated loon (*Gavia arctica*), or some other waterfowl, adorning the water mirror of the most beautiful European karst lakes. While wandering around or looking for food, a very rare species can be found here, such as golden-eagle (*Aquila chrysaetos*), falcon (*Falco subbuteo*), and peregrine falcon (*Falco peregrinus*).

There are over 50 mammal species registered in the Plitviče Lakes National Park, most of which are bats with as many as 22 species, all of which are covered by the Directive on the Protection of Natural Habitats and Wild Flora and Fauna. Some of the most specific species of bats that inhabit this beautiful area are *Barbastella barbastellus*, *Miniopterus schreibersii*, *Myotis capaccinii*, *Myotis myotis*, *Rhinolophus Euryale*, and *Rhinolophus ferrumequinum* [116-121].

Among the large mammals in the park were recorded *Ursus arctos* (brown bear), *Canis lupus* (wolf), *Lynx lynx* (lynx), *Meles meles* (badger), *Martes martes* (pine-marten), and *Lutra lutra* (otter). Otter *Lutra lutra* and *Lynx lynx* are on the endangered species list, and all species love secluded and peaceful areas it is extremely rare to see them in the park because they often seek shelter during the day.

Dinaric vole (*Dinaromys bogdanovi*), also known as Balkan snow vole, an endemic species of Dinaric karst, lives at the mountain crests, on a stony base in the larger Park area. This species has adjusted to life in rocky fissures. Their settlements are built in karst caves and holes. It is a living fossil, an example of the Tertiary period, the only living species in the tribe Pliomyini, and might arguably better be placed in Pliomys, a genus established for its fossil relatives even before the Balkan snow vole was scientifically described [122].

All photos presented in this report were realized by Fabio Rossano Dario and Cristina De Vincenzo, using a digital photo camera Canon PowerShot.

CONCLUSIONS

Plitviče Lakes National Park is one of the most beautiful and interesting parks in Croatia and Europe. It encompasses an area of just under 300 square kilometers with the lakes themselves comprising just 1% of this expanse. The remainder of the park is made up of a wooded forest of beech, fir, and pine trees. These natural environments host a wide variety of plant and animal species, some endemic, others endangered. The Plitviče Lakes National Park is a very interesting geological and hydrogeological karst phenomenon and is proudly listed on the UNESCO World Heritage List, and because of its exceptional beauty and specific flora and fauna, it is a symbol of world tourism.

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Photo 1. The Bellevue Hotel is situated near to the Plitviče Lakes National Park entrance. The hotel offers you a peaceful rest in a unique natural surroundings.

Photo 2. The Bellevue Hotel was built in 1963 and is recognizable for its interesting interior and exterior using wood.

Photo 3. Detail of the information center, with restrooms and picnic area.

Photo 4. Parts of the park are also connected by boats.

Photo 5. There are two boats in the Plitviče Lakes National Park. One of them crosses the big lake Kozjak.

Photo 6. Ferry boat on the lake, Plitviče Lakes National Park in autumn.

Photo 7. Signposts are distributed along the trails, showing the trails (C and E) and the bus stop.

Photo 8. Signposts are distributed along the trails. They were made of wood and are in perfect harmony with the environment.

Photo 9. The park has many signposts, such as prohibited access to protect the ecosystems.

Photo 10. The park is full of boardwalks like this one.

Photo 11. Wooden walkway with handrail in Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 12. Wooden walkway with a bridge crossing a small stream in the park.

Photo 13. Small viewpoint from where you can have a beautiful view of the lakes.

Photo 14. Detail of a soil protection against erosion.

Photo 15. Autumn leaf color, in various shades of yellow, orange, red, purple, and brown is one of the attractions in the Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 16. The Plitviče Lakes National Park is heavily forested, mostly with beech, spruce, and fir trees, and features a mixture of Alpine and Mediterranean vegetation.

Photo 17. Plitviče Lakes National Park is known for its natural beauty.

Photo 18. The waterfall Veliki Prštavci at the Upper Lakes.

Photo 19. The park is peaceful and has many nice spots for meditation.

Photo 20. Wood bridge over the lake.

Photo 21. The view looks at the walkway of a wooden bridge surrounded by shrubs.

Photo 22. Stream flowing under a wood bridge.

Photo 23. Plitviče Lakes National Park, and the integration of infrastructure and landscape.

Photo 24. Small waterfalls like these are located throughout the park.

Photo 25. Fallen leaves over the water.

Photo 26. An autumn leaf in the Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 27. Fallen leaves on the trail indicate the autumn season.

Photo 28. Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 29. Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 30. The park is peaceful and has many nice spots for meditation.

Photo 31. A boardwalk following one of the smaller lakes.

Photo 32. Wooden walkway along the waterfalls.

Photo 33. Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 34. The iron handrail ensures the safety of walkers in dangerous areas.

Photo 35. The great plant diversity creates a fascinating interplay of colors that change with the seasons. The lakes are surrounded by forests.

Photo 36. Mixed woodland with silver fir (*Abies alba*) spruce (*Picea excelsa*) and European beeches (*Fagus sylvatica*) in the Plitviče Lakes National Park, Croatia, October 2019.

Photo 37. The lakes are surrounded by forests.

Photo 38. Plitvice Lakes National Park is known for its abundance of beautiful lakes.

Photo 39. Wooden plank walkway in Plitviče Lakes National Park. The wooden boardwalk path stretches for dozens of miles.

Photo 40. Wooden walkway across a protected marsh and wetlands.

Photo 41. In general, the trails are not challenging and appropriate for a variety of ages and fitness levels.

Photo 42. Resting with an amazing panoramic view.

Photo 43. The Wooden plank walkway is integrated with the landscape in the Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 44. Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 45. Explanation of the dynamics of the formation of the tufa barriers.

Photo 46. In the Plitvice Lakes, the tufa-formation process in which tufa barriers form and grow is highly complex.

Photo 47. Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 48. Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 49. Wooden walkway with handrail in the park.

Photo 50. The iron handrail ensures the safety of walkers in dangerous areas.

Photo 51. Autumn leaf color, in various shades of yellow, orange, red, purple, and brown is one of the attractions in the Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 52. Plitviče Lakes National Park is known for its natural beauty.

Photo 53. Flocks of wild ducks (*Anas platyrhynchos*) are frequent in the Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 54. The landscape of the Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 55. In addition to species from the plant and animal world, the park is also abundant in fungi species. Fungi are a very significant group of organisms.

Photo 56. Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 57. Wooden paths by the lakeside in Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 58. Wooden elevated walkway, on the right side is a natural cave.

Photo 59. The wooden handrail ensures the safety of walkers and is in harmony with the environment.

Photo 60. Detail of the wooden handrail along the trail.

Photo 61. Mallard (*Anas platyrhynchos*) is the most recognized waterfowl in the world. Most often, they prefer wetlands, where waters produce large amounts of floating, emergent, and submerged vegetation and also produce many aquatic invertebrates on which mallards feed.

Photo 62. The European chub (*Squalius cephalus*) is in clean water. Observe the lucidity and clarity of the water.

Photo 63. The robin (*Erithacus rubecula*) inhabits farmland and woodland, as well as gardens and parks in towns and cities. Its diet consists of seeds, fruits, insects, worms, and other invertebrates.

Photo 64. A stream flows under a wooden bridge.

Photo 65. Wooden elevated footpath in the forest.

Photo 66. Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 67. Wooden bench on a walkway in Park.

Photo 68. The Plitviče Lakes National Park has a notably wide variety of plant communities, due to its range of microclimates, differing soils, and varying levels of altitude.

Photo 69. Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 70. Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 71. Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 72. Bog habitats and their vegetation in Croatia, as well as in the park, are relics of the glacial period.

Photo 73. The white butterbur (*Petasites albus*) is a flowering plant species from the family Asteraceae. It is native to central Europe and the Caucasus. It prefers damp soils in deciduous forests, mountain pastures, springs, and streamsides.

Photo 74. Waterfall near Gradinsko jezero.

Photo 75. Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 76. The landscape of the Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 77. The walking trails in the park are well conserved and safe.

Photo 78. The walking trails in the park are well conserved and safe.

Photo 79. Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 80. The Lower Lakes canyon.

Photo 81. A barrier between the lakes Gavanovac and Kaluđerovac.

Photo 82. Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 83. A wonderful piece of nature in Plitviče Lakes. The lakes are famous for their distinctive colors, ranging from azure to green, grey, or blue...

Photo 84. The colors change constantly depending on the number of minerals or organisms in the water and the angle of sunlight.

Photo 85. Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 86. The landscape of the Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 87. Veliki Slap, also known as the Great Waterfall.

Photo 88. Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 89. Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 90. Sastavci waterfalls, Lower Lakes, Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 91. Plitviče Lakes is heavily forested, mainly with spruce, beech, and fir trees.

Photo 92. Bridge over a river with a small waterfall.

Photo 93. Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 94. Look at the water anywhere in the park and you will sure to see fishes.

Photo 95. The lakes are all interconnected and follow the water flow. They are separated by natural dams of travertine, which is deposited by the action of algae, moss, and bacteria.

Photo 96. Paradise waterfalls of Plitviče Lakes National Park, panoramic view, Croatia.

Photo 97. Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 98. Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 99. The landscape of turquoise lake in Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 100. Plitviče Lakes National Park is known for its natural beauty.